

SOLVING HIGHER DEGREE EQUATIONS

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.Annotation: This article presents some methods for solving higher order equations.

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The fundamental theorem of algebra:

$$a_n x^n + a_{n-1} x^{n-1} + \dots + a_1 x + a_0 = 0 \quad (1)$$

although it implies that there are n solutions to the equation, in general it does not specify algorithms for finding solutions. Solving equation (1) has been a difficult problem until now, and it has been solved only in some special cases.

If the solution of the equation (1) is determined by the expression formed by performing the operations of addition, subtraction, multiplication, division and extraction of roots on the coefficients of the equation, then the equation (1) is said to be solved in radicals.

Reminder. If $\alpha = a + bi$ complex number is a solution of equation (1), α number joint $\bar{\alpha} = a - bi$ complex number is also a solution of equation (1).

Now let's look at some cases where equation (1) is solved in radicals.

Obviously, $n = 2$ when equation (1) comes to the previously studied quadratic equation: $ax^2 + bx + c = 0$

This equation always has two roots:

$$x_1 = \frac{-b + \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}, \quad x_2 = \frac{-b - \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}$$

(discriminant $b^2 - 4ac > 0$ when, x_1 and x_2 are real and distinct numbers;
 $b^2 - 4ac = 0$ when $x_1 = x_2$ is a multiple of the root; $b^2 - 4ac < 0$ when x_1
and x_2 are mutually exclusive complex numbers).

Now we consider the following special cases of equation (1).

a) $n = 3$ let it be In these cases, equation (1).

$$a_0x^3 + a_1x^2 + a_2x + a_3 = 0$$

appears. For convenience, the key equation is as follows

$$a_0x^3 + a_1x^2 + a_2x + a_3 = 0 \quad (a_0 \neq 0) \quad (2)$$

we can record. Equation (2) is solved as follows:

1) Dividing both sides of equation (2) by , we find:

$$x^3 + b_1x^2 + b_2x + b_3 = 0 \quad (3)$$

In this $b_k = \frac{a_k}{a_0}$ ($k = 1, 2, 3$)

$$1) (3) \text{ in Eq } x = y - \frac{b_1}{3}$$

we will replace. Then the left side of equation (3) is this

$$\left(y - \frac{b_1}{3}\right)^3 + b_1\left(y - \frac{b_1}{3}\right)^2 + b_2\left(y - \frac{b_1}{3}\right) + b_3 =$$

$$y^3 + \left(b_2 - \frac{b_1^2}{3}\right)y + \left(b_2 - \frac{b_1b_2}{3} + \frac{2}{27}b_1^3\right)$$

it looks like the following

$$\left(b_2 - \frac{b_1^2}{3}\right) = p, \quad \left(b_2 - \frac{b_1 b_2}{3} + \frac{2}{27} b_1^3\right) = q$$

equation (3) after substitution

$$y^3 + py + q = 0 \quad (4)$$

Takes the form.

2) (4) the solution of the equation

$$y = u + v \quad (5)$$

we look for in the form, where u and v are these

$$u \cdot v = -\frac{p}{3} \quad (6)$$

is required to satisfy the condition.

Evidently, u and v considered from relations (5) and (6) are as follows

$$t^2 - yt - \frac{p}{3} = 0$$

it follows that the roots of the quadratic equation (Viet's theorem).

3) $y = u + v$ in (4) we substitute y in the equation:

$$(u+v)^3 + p(u+v) + q = 0$$

As a result

$$u^3 + 3u^2v + 3uv^2 + v^3 + pu + pv + q = 0$$

ie

$$(u^3 + v^3 + q) + (3uv + p)(u+v) = 0$$

(7)

Will be.

Known, $u \cdot v = -\frac{p}{3}$. In it $3uv + p = 0$ is, equation (7).

$$u^3 + v^3 + q = 0 \quad , \text{ ie } \quad u^3 + v^3 = -q$$

appears. So,

$$y^3 + py + q = 0$$

solving this equation

$$\begin{cases} u^3 + v^3 = -q \\ u^3 \cdot v^3 = -\frac{p^3}{27} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

comes to solve the system.

4) It can be seen from equations (8) that u^3 and v^3 s these

$$t^2 + qt - \frac{p^3}{27} = 0$$

will be the solutions of the quadratic equation. We solve this quadratic equation:

$$t_1 = -\frac{q}{2} + \sqrt{\frac{q^2}{4} + \frac{p^3}{27}}, \quad t_2 = -\frac{q}{2} - \sqrt{\frac{q^2}{4} + \frac{p^3}{27}}$$

So,

$$u^3 = t_1 = -\frac{q}{2} + \sqrt{\frac{q^2}{4} + \frac{p^3}{27}} \quad (9)$$

$$v^3 = t_2 = -\frac{q}{2} - \sqrt{\frac{q^2}{4} + \frac{p^3}{27}} \quad (10)$$

6) (9) and (10) from the equations

$$\begin{aligned} u &= \sqrt[3]{-\frac{q}{2} + \sqrt{\frac{q^2}{4} + \frac{p^3}{27}}} \\ v &= \sqrt[3]{-\frac{q}{2} - \sqrt{\frac{q^2}{4} + \frac{p^3}{27}}} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

we find that Hence, the solution of equation (4).

$$y = u + v = \sqrt[3]{-\frac{q}{2} + \sqrt{\frac{q^2}{4} + \frac{p^3}{27}}} + \sqrt[3]{-\frac{q}{2} - \sqrt{\frac{q^2}{4} + \frac{p^3}{27}}} \quad (12)$$

Will be.

(12) the equality is called Cardano's formula. This is the formula

$$u+v$$

consists of a sum, and each u and v has three values. Then the values of u+v sum will be 9. Among these values, only three are solutions of equation (4), and the values of such u and v are as follows

$$uv = -\frac{p}{3}$$

will relate.

7) Suppose u and v are one of the values of equations (11).

u_1 and v_1 let it be In it

$$u_2 = \frac{-1 + \sqrt{3} \cdot i}{2} u_1,$$

$$u_3 = \frac{-1 - \sqrt{3} \cdot i}{2} u_1,$$

$$v_2 = \frac{-1 - \sqrt{3} \cdot i}{2} v_1,$$

$$v_3 = \frac{-1 + \sqrt{3} \cdot i}{2} v_1$$

Will be.

7) (4) solutions of Eq

$$\begin{aligned} y_1 &= u_1 + v_1 \\ y_2 &= -\frac{1}{2}(u_1 + v_1) + \frac{\sqrt{3} \cdot i}{2}(u_1 - v_1) \\ y_3 &= -\frac{1}{2}(u_1 + v_1) - \frac{\sqrt{3} \cdot i}{2}(u_1 - v_1) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

are the solutions of the given equation

$$x_1 = y_1 - \frac{b_1}{3}, \quad x_2 = y_2 - \frac{b_1}{3}, \quad x_3 = y_3 - \frac{b_1}{3}$$

Will be.

1-misol. *This,*

$$x^3 - 9x^2 + 21x - 5 = 0$$

solve the equation.

◀ In the given equation

$$x = y + 3$$

we will replace. In it

$$(y+3)^3 - 9(y+3)^2 + 21(y+3) - 5 = 0$$

ie

$$y^3 - 6y + 4 = 0$$

will be. (12) we find using the formula.

$$u = \sqrt[3]{-2 + \sqrt{4-8}} = \sqrt[3]{-2+2i}$$

Obviously, this is one of the values of the cube root

$$u_1 = 1+i$$

Will be. In it

$$v_1 = \frac{6}{3(1+i)} = 1-i$$

is, according to formula (13).

$$y_1 = 2, \quad y_2 = -1 - \sqrt{3}, \quad y_3 = -1 + \sqrt{3}$$

will be. Hence, the solutions of the given equation

$$x_1 = 5, \quad x_2 = 2 - \sqrt{3}, \quad x_3 = 2 + \sqrt{3}$$

Will be. ►

a) $n = 4$ let it be In this case, equation (1).

$$a_4x^4 + a_3x^3 + a_2x^2 + a_1x + a_0 = 0 \quad (14)$$

appears. Equation (14) is solved in radicals. It has a solution algorithm.

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